

EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE – AN EMPIRICAL STUDY WITH PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS

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Abstract

Emotional Intelligence (EI) is critical to the success of organizations including banking sectors. Now-a-days, emotional intelligence has been evolved as a topic of greatest important. In fact, there is substantial evidence that emotional intelligence is more important than job specific skills and knowledge. Different jobs require employees of different level of emotional intelligence. Emotional Intelligence has become increasingly relevant to organizational development and developing individuals, because the Emotional Quotient (EQ) principles provide a new way to understand and assess people's behavior, in managing stress, job performance and organizational commitment. In point of this view, the researchers aimed to examine the effect of emotional intelligence among private sector bank employees in Erode. The nature of this study is empirical method. Sample size of 95 private sector bank employees were selected. The sample selection is completed by approaching random sampling method. A self-structured questionnaire has been administered in order to collect primary data related to socio-economic profile and effect of emotional intelligence. The responses on emotional intelligence have been collected and computed by using 5 points Likert's scale and the secondary data were gathered through published article, books, journals, internet sources, etc. Statistical techniques like percentage analysis, mean score, standard deviation and ANOVA are used for analysis. In this study, the null hypothesis is developed to examine the significant difference in mean effect of emotional intelligence with regard to selected variables. This study found from analysis that high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who belong to 41-50 years of age group, assistant manager, working in urban area bank, 11-15 years of working experience and working for 9-10 hours daily.

Keywords: Employees, Private Sector Bank, Emotional Intelligence, Managing Stress, Job Performance, Organizational Commitment, Etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indian Banking is the lifeline of nation and its people. Banking has developed vital sectors of the economy and usher in a new dawn of progress on the Indian horizon. The sector has translated the hopes and aspirations of millions of people into reality. In contemporary competitive world, banks play an important role in attaining the objective of economic development through financing every sector of the economy and help for the smooth operation. Private sector banks are a crucial part of the banking system and play a significant role in the country's economic growth. Understanding the functions of private sector banks, as well as how they differ from public sector banks, is key to recognizing their importance in the financial system. Emotional intelligence is a fundamental concept

in today's world because it helps understand and feel another person's situation. It is essential not only in the workplace but also in personal life to make sound decisions. It is becoming increasingly important in organisations because it aids in the development of solid relationships with peers, subordinates, and others. It aids in the implementation of motivation and positive leadership in the workplace. Emotional intelligence is also critical in making effective decisions that benefit both the organisation and the employees. Emotional intelligence can help a person become mentally strong and handle a situation effectively. Emotional intelligence is essential in leadership because it fosters empathy for others and helps them become a better leader. It benefits organisations by motivating employees to work toward common goals and objectives. A lack of emotional intelligence in leaders and employees at work steers the organisation in the wrong direction, resulting in demotivation, bullying, and harassment. On the other hand, it aids in developing solid workplace relationships and the improvement of employee performance. It increases employee productivity and efficiency.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Sakshee Rastogi and Manoj Agarwal (2024) revealed that there were a number of factors influenced a employee's emotional intelligence, including their age and gender, amongst others. Also, quantity of work experience of employees was one of a number of additional factors whereas there was a significant relationship between the factors of emotional intelligence and work experience. But, having a very significant job experience that had a negative impact was associated with having self-awareness. The researchers Vishant Vijay Chimate and Shailesh Kr. Pathak (2022) mentioned as a result of conducting an exhaustive study on a variety of aspects, including self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy, and motivation, it had become apparent that the private sector and public sector banks displayed distinct patterns of emotional intelligence among their workforces. In addition, employees at private sector banks seemed to have a higher degree of emotional intelligence, which was defined by their ability to comprehend and control their emotions, cultivate healthy interpersonal connections, and successfully navigated the problems that come with working in a dynamic financial environment. The study of Amarjeet et al. (2020) inferred that women in the private banking sector were not emotionally strong. Thus, they couldn't control their emotions and feelings when they were frustrated. Hence, this study stated that with all of these issues, one can stabilize their emotions by implementing practices such as removing negative thoughts from one's mind, controlling stress, and adhering to the recommended practices to become more emotionally intelligent.

The author Neeraj Gogia (2020) majority of respondents had a high level of Emotional Intelligence as well as strong personal and social competence self-ratings. Also, bank employees' overall perception on the five dimensions of emotional intelligence such as self-awareness, managing emotions, self-motivation, recognizing others' emotions, and handling the relationship. Moreover, the employees of HDFC Bank were highly emotionally intelligent followed by ICICI Bank, Axis Bank and Kotak Mahindra Bank employees. In view of Agilandeswari and Lakshmi Bala (2019) explored that self-

mindfulness, empathy, self-inspiration and managing relations were equivalent in both open and private bank employees. Also, emotional security was powerful in open sector bank employees than employees of private banks. Further, the connection between demographic profile and emotional intelligence factors uncovered that female employees were increasingly powerful in every one of the characteristics of emotional intelligence in both Public and Private Banks. The result of Bhanu Priya (2018) justified that both public and private sector bank managers had no significant difference on emotional intelligence scale, private sector bank. Furthermore, there was a significant difference among top level, middle level and lower-level bank managers on emotional intelligence. So, the banks' human resource department should try to provide different training programs, organize various workshops, as well as create positive environment to motivate their managers to attend such programs and workshops.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Private sector banks have a group of individuals or private companies which own the majority of the equity of any given bank. In India, the swift service provided by a majority of the private banks also providing customized financial plans to cater to the needs and requirements of the customers. The workplace that is high in stress is one in which the constant pursuit of objectives, together with the duty of handling financial transactions and the expectations of customers, adds to the environment. Emotional Intelligence enables employees to understand and empathize with customers' financial concerns and emotions. Emotional intelligence is a vital skill for private bank employees which enhances customer relationships, improves communication, promotes stress management, fosters leadership and teamwork, and encourages ethical decision-making. Not many studies are undertaken in the study area. Hence, this study is aimed to analyze the effect of emotional intelligence among selected employees of private sector bank in Erode.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the socio-economic profile of the selected employees working in private sector banks in Erode.
- To examine the effect of emotional intelligence on employee performance in the study area.

5. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to designation of the employees.
- There is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to experience of the employees.
- There is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to daily working hours of the employees.

6. RESEARCH METHODS

This study has used a descriptive research strategy. The authors have collected data from both primary and secondary sources. The target population are employees who working in private sector bank in Erode, Tamil Nadu. A structured questionnaire has been developed and distributed among the population in order to get primary data regarding socio-economic profile and effect of emotional intelligence whereas the secondary data also are obtained from published articles, books, journals, and online sources, among others.

The sample size has been involved of 95 employees of private sector bank through random sampling method. The collected data have been entered into the MS-Excel software and analyzed through several statistical tools including percentage analysis, mean score, standard deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) via SPSS 26.0 software.

7. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Socio-Economic Profile of the Employees

The collected details of socio-economic profile and effect of emotional intelligence among selected employees have been furnished in the following table.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

No.	Variables Name	Number of Respondents	%	Mean	SD
1	Age				
	• Below 30 years	18	18.9	3.64	0.55
	• 30 - 40 years	37	39.0	3.61	0.45
	• 41 - 50 years	25	26.3	3.67	0.46
	• Above 50 years	15	15.8	3.54	0.56
	Total	95	100.0		
2	Designation				
	• Clerk	36	37.9	3.50	0.53
	• Cashier	25	26.3	3.47	0.61
	• Assistant Manager	21	22.1	3.72	0.45
	• Manager	13	13.7	3.44	0.44
	Total	95	100.0		
3	Bank Location				
	• Urban	32	33.7	3.98	0.32
	• Semi-Urban	45	47.4	3.18	0.38
	• Rural	18	18.9	3.60	0.51
	Total	95	100.0		
4	Working Experience				
	• Upto 5 years	15	15.8	3.60	0.47
	• 6 – 10 years	23	24.2	3.39	0.55
	• 11 – 15 years	32	33.7	4.05	0.33
	• Above 15 years	25	26.3	3.34	0.43
	Total	95	100.0		

No.	Variables Name	Number of Respondents	%	Mean	SD
5	Daily Working Hours				
	• Upto 8 hours	25	26.3	3.10	0.36
	• 9 – 10 hours	30	31.6	3.89	0.37
	• 11 – 12 hours	23	24.2	3.33	0.51
	• Above 12 hours	17	17.9	3.86	0.40
	Total	95	100.0		

From the above table, it is inferred that

- 18.9% of the employees are belong to upto 30 years of age group, 39.0% of the employees are belong to 30-40 years, 26.3% of the employees as 41-50 years and 15.8% of the employees are belong to age category of above 50 years.
- It is determined that 37.9% of the employees are working as clerk in private bank, 26.3% of the employees are cashiers, 22.1% of the employees are assistant managers and 13.7% of the employees are managers in private sector banks.
- It is observed that 33.7% of the employees are working in urban area private banks, 47.4% of the employees are working in semi-urban area and 18.9% of the employees are working in rural area private banks.
- It is cleared that 15.8% of the employees have upto 5 years of working experience, 24.2% of the employees have working experience for 6-10 years, 33.7% of the employees are belong to 11-15 years and 26.3% of the employees have above 15 years of working experience.
- It is inferred that 26.3% of the employees work upto 8 hours daily, 31.6% of the employees work for 9-10 hours every day, 24.2% of the employees are working for 11-12 hours and 17.9% of the employees are working above 12 hours in private sector banks.

7.2 Effect of Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence helps bank employees actively listen to customers' needs and concerns, improving communication and understanding which is essential for resolving conflicts effectively and maintaining positive working relationships.

For this study, the researchers have framed eight statements with regard to effect of emotional intelligence. It is noticed from the analysis that the Cronbach Alpha value for the statements of effect of emotional intelligence is 0.893.

This study indicates that the reliability of the effect of emotional intelligence is good and fit for analysis. It is indicated among effect of emotional intelligence that most of the bank employees opined as 'I am able to recognize and manage my emotions' with the mean score and standard deviation of 3.98 and 1.15 respectively followed by 'I usually avoid conflicts and negotiations with other people' with the mean score and standard deviation of 3.95 and 1.08 respectively.

Testing of Hypothesis (ANOVA)

7.3 Relationship between Socio-Economic Profile and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

This section has analyzed that the relationship between the socio-economic profile and effect of emotional intelligence in Erode. A hypothesis has been framed in order to analyse the relationship between selected independent variables and effect of emotional intelligence through ANOVA.

Designation and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

H₀: There is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to designation of the employees.

Table 2: Designation and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	'p' value
Between Groups	1.020	3	0.340	1.243	0.299 ^{NS}
Within Groups	24.889	91	0.274		
Total	25.909	94			

Note: NS - Not Significant

It is pointed out from the analysis that the 'p' value is greater than 0.05 accordingly the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to designation of the employees.

Experience and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

H₀: There is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to experience of the employees.

Table 3: Experience and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	'p' value
Between Groups	5.562	3	1.854	8.291	0.000*
Within Groups	20.347	91	0.224		
Total	25.909	94			

Note: * - Significant at 1% level

It is assumed from the analysis that the 'p' value is lesser than 0.05 consequently the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is a significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to experience of the employees.

Daily Working Hours and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

H₀: There is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to daily working hours of the employees.

Table 4: Daily Working Hours and Effect of Emotional Intelligence

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	'p' value
Between Groups	10.558	3	3.519	20.863	0.000*
Within Groups	15.351	91	0.169		
Total	25.909	94			

Note: * - Significant at 1% level

It is revealed from the analysis that the 'p' value is lesser than 0.05 then the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to daily working hours of the employees.

8. FINDINGS

- It is showed from the analysis that majority of the employees are belong to age category of 30-40 years. Also, high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who belong to 41-50 years of age group.
- It is mentioned from the analysis that majority of the employees are working as clerk. Further, high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who working as assistant manager.
- It is indicated from the analysis that majority of the employees are working in semi-urban area private banks. Additionally, high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who working in urban area private banks.
- It is revealed from the analysis that majority of the employees have 11-15 years of working experience in private banks. Thus, high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who belong to 11-15 years of working experience.
- It is confirmed from the analysis that majority of the employees are working for 9-10 hours daily. Further, high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who working for 9-10 hours daily.
- It is examined from the mean score test that among effect of emotional intelligence, most of the bank employees opined as 'able to recognize and manage emotions' with the mean score followed by 'usually avoid conflicts and negotiations with other people' with the mean score of 3.98 and 3.95 respectively.
- The 'F' test assumed that there is no significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to designation of the employees.
- It is justified from ANOVA that there is a significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to experience of the employees.
- From 'F' test, it could be observed that there is a significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to daily working hours of the employees.

9. SUGGESTIONS

- The findings mentioned that high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who belong to 41-50 years of age group. Hence, it is suggested that private sector bank should assess first where their employees lack with low emotional intelligence and should create positive environment to motivate their employees.
- It could be observed from the analysis that high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who working as assistant manager. So, the private sector banks should try to provide different training programs, organize various workshops to motivate their employees to get high level of emotional intelligence.
- From the study, it is measured that high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who working in urban area private banks. Therefore, all the private sector banks should make their employees to control their emotions and deal with difficult situations to enhance their emotional intelligence.
- This study justified from the analysis that high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who belong to 11-15 years of working experience. So, the private sector banks should conduct such programs and workshops that lead to the development of the employees to manage their emotions.
- From the findings, it is evaluated that high level effect of emotional intelligence is perceived by the employees who working for 9-10 hours daily. So, the pressures come from a variety of causes, including but not limited to one's workload, the haziness of one's function, interpersonal disputes, and the ongoing need to adjust to changing financial environments.

10. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to examine the effect of emotional intelligence among selected employees of private sector bank in Erode. Emotional intelligence is a crucial skill for private bank employees as it significantly impacts their interactions with customers, colleagues, and overall job performance. This study confirmed that there is a significant mean difference in effect of emotional intelligence with regard to selected variables like experience and daily working hours of the employees. To maintain emotional intelligence, private sector bank employees with low emotional intelligence should first recognise negative emotions and then eliminate them as well as they should work on stress management, which they can do by participating in exercise or other activities.

References

- 1) Agilandeswari, N., & Lakshmi Bala, M. (2019). A study on emotional intelligence in banks - An empirical study with reference to selected banks of Thanjavur District. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, 7(2), 190-194.
- 2) Amarjeet, Ruchika Choudhary, Abhimanyu Bhardwaj, & Kaushalendra Pal Singh, (2020). Emotional intelligence in employees working in the banking sector: An empirical study of Delhi. *J Crit Rev*, 7(1), 2089-2093.

- 3) Bhanu Priya, (2018). Emotional intelligence: A study on public and private sector bank managers. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 209-216.
- 4) Gupta, S.L. (2007). *Marketing Research*. 1st Edition, New Delhi: Excel Books.
- 5) Kothari C.R. (2016). *Research Methodology: Methods & Techniques*. 3rd Edition, New Age International (P) Limited, Publishers, New Delhi.
- 6) Neeraj Gogia, (2020). A Descriptive Study of Indian Private Sector Banks in Agra Region-With Special Reference to Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Service Quality. *ADHYAYAN*, 10(2), 82-87.
- 7) Rajendra Nargundkar, (2019). *Marketing Research - Text and Cases*. 4th Edition, McGraw hill Education (India) Private Limited, Chennai.
- 8) Sakshee Rastogi, & Manoj Agarwal, (2024). Emotional Intelligence among Banking Professionals. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 4(1), 471-483.
- 9) Vishant Vijay Chimate, & Shailesh KR. Pathak, (2022). Impact of emotional intelligence in bank employees in India. *International Journal for Innovative Engineering and Management Research*, 11(12), 2166-2174.